

US Astronomy Community Surveys for the US-ELTP

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The role of NSF’s NOIRLab in the US Extremely Large Telescope Program (US-ELTP) is to provide user services spanning the full research life cycle from proposal preparation through data analysis and publication for US users of the Giant Magellan Telescope (GMT) and the Thirty Meter Telescope (TMT). One of the program’s challenges is to ensure inclusive support for a broad community of observers and archival researchers. There are many ways to design such support, but the best way to make sure that it answers users’ needs is to ask them directly.

Regular broad consultation with the astronomy community will be the norm throughout the development of the US-ELTP software tools and user support models. In the current early phase of the project, NOIRLab has conducted two surveys to grab a snapshot of users’ needs and expectations. One survey was open to every astronomer in the US, while the second targeted the PIs of current and past Large and Long Programs (LLPs) at the International Gemini Observatory. We were pleased by the replies to both surveys.

Survey of the broad US astronomy community¹

The goal of this survey was to assess the US astronomy community’s potential interest in using data from GMT and TMT for their science. We also wanted to learn what data products and data services would be helpful. We wanted

¹ The margin of error is 7.24%, with a 95% confidence level (19 times over 20).

Anticipated community dependence on US-ELTP analysis tools

Figure 1: Distribution of responses based on answers to the question “How much would you anticipate relying on analysis tools provided by NOIRLab?” Credit: A.-N. Chené/NOIRLab

feedback on two core questions: 1) Are US-ELTP high-level requirements for data services aligned with the needs of the community? and 2) How should we rank requirements by order of priority so we can plan future work efficiently? Eight questions were designed around the key elements of data reduction and analysis.

The majority of the respondents expect to use standard data reduction pipelines for GMT/TMT instruments rather than their own tools. Those who disagreed with this approach were not confident that the quality of the results from standard pipelines will be sufficient. This shows that not only will the pipelines need to be openly accessible and properly supported but also their output will need to comply with high-quality standards that will have to be clearly demonstrated, documented, and publicized.

Support for analysis tools provided by NOIRLab was much more nuanced. When asked how much they would anticipate relying on analysis tools provided by NOIRLab, respondents said, at ~20%, “a little” or “not at all”; at ~30%, “moderately”; and at ~30%, “very much” or “extremely” (Figure 1). There is therefore a need for support with basic analysis work, such as spectral fitting or PSF photometry, mostly from potential users who are not familiar with optical and infrared data or junior researchers who have limited experience. A certain number of respondents mentioned that without any support they may simply not be able to perform their analysis successfully.

The most popular observing mode the respondents expect to use on GMT and TMT was integral field spectroscopy (50%). All of the spectroscopic modes (long-slit, multi-object, and

high-resolution), as well as broadband and high-contrast imaging, shared a comparable level of popularity (40%+). 10% of the respondents would like to use modes that are not currently planned for GMT or TMT, such as polarimetry and Fabry-Pérot spectroscopy.

Unfortunately, the survey was not successful in achieving broad demographic representation. Only a third of the respondents were junior faculty, postdocs, or students. A small portion (7.8%) were from a two- or four-year college; 14.5% were affiliated with a minority-serving institution (MSI), and one respondent's affiliation was classified as a Historically Black College and University (HBCU) or Tribal College. Future survey efforts will focus specifically on junior researchers, as well as researchers at small or under-resourced institutions (SUIs).

Survey of LLP PIs²

LLPs at Gemini are similar to the expected Key Science Programs at GMT and TMT. These are programs that require a large amount of observing time and/or a large number of consecutive semesters to complete. They are ambitious programs that aim at making highly impactful new discoveries. And, most importantly, they are large collaborations between people across the whole Gemini partnership. The US-ELTP staff were interested in learning more about how LLP science teams formed and communicated, what their biggest obstacles were, and what their general level of appreciation was for the technical support that was provided to them.

Every respondent said that the science team was formed either from usual collaborators or by direct invitations to individuals or groups. No one offered an open collaboration through a broad announcement. While this is not unexpected, it is a practice that will probably have to evolve to foster more inclusion of a diverse group of researchers in the near future.

There appear to be two groups with different approaches to team coordination. One group relied on conventional modes of communication, such as videoconferences (Zoom or Meet), emails, the phone, or in-person meetings. While this is a more natural approach, the main challenges were restrictions due to the COVID-19 pandemic and time zone differences. The other group used the instant messaging platform Slack, which was praised for easing quick communication and for conducting a

discussion in a much more efficient way than a meeting or an email thread. However, some threads were not well-organized, and it was difficult to keep track of conversations or to find old messages. Also, because not everyone is on Slack, it could not be mandated as the official way to communicate within a team.

Collaborative work on the proposal was usually supported by the cloud-based LaTeX editor Overleaf. Most respondents had positive comments on the platform although they occasionally had minor issues. The respondents with a paid license had a better experience than those using the free version.

No respondent noted any serious roadblocks. Access to licenses was generally not an issue, yet when it was, the LLP science team was able to work with free software. A few obstacles were occasionally met during data reduction and analysis, but the team was able to handle these obstacles effectively. The majority (75%) have made advanced data products available for public release.

The next step

The results of the two surveys are already guiding the requirements for the development of the US-ELTP operation systems. They will also guide future consultations that will be more focused towards junior researchers and researchers at SUIs.

The US-ELTP thanks everyone who answered our surveys. There is a lot more information in the responses than has been presented here, and the text comments are rich in valuable information.

The US Extremely Large Telescope Program (US-ELTP) is an endeavor to develop a two-telescope, two-hemisphere single system for the next generation of ground-based telescopes. Scientists at US institutions will have equal opportunity to access 25% of the observing time on the Giant Magellan Telescope (GMT) and the Thirty Meter Telescope (TMT) to observe objects anywhere in the sky and carry out transformational research. NOIRLab will facilitate an open peer-review process, archive all science data from both observatories, and provide an extensive suite of user support and data analysis services.

² The response rate was 50%